

INDIVIDUALIZED HOMOEOPATHIC MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE MENORRHAGIA WITH RAPID CLINICAL IMPROVEMENT: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Menorrhagia is a frequent gynecological problem in young women and may be triggered or exacerbated by emotional stress. Homeopathy emphasizes individualized treatment based on constitutional and emotional factors. This case report describes the homeopathic management of acute, painless menorrhagia following an emotional insult. **Methods:** A 21-year-old female presenting with sudden-onset, painless menorrhagia after a significant emotional stressor was evaluated. A detailed clinical and constitutional assessment was performed, encompassing mental, physical, and menstrual characteristics. Based on the totality of symptoms, *Calcarea carbonica* was prescribed. The primary outcome was cessation of uterine bleeding. Secondary outcomes included changes in emotional well-being, general health, and menstrual regularity. Causal attribution between the remedy and clinical outcome was assessed using the MONARCH (Improved Modified Naranjo) criteria. Follow-up was conducted over subsequent

menstrual cycles. **Results:** Complete cessation of uterine bleeding occurred within 24 hours of remedy administration. Improvement in emotional stability and general health was noted during follow-up. Subsequent menstrual cycles were regular, with no recurrence of menorrhagia. The MONARCH score supported a probable causal relationship between the intervention and the observed outcome. **Conclusion:** This case suggests a positive role of individualized homeopathic treatment in managing emotionally precipitated menorrhagia, highlighting the importance of constitutional assessment in clinical practice.

KEYWORDS: Menorrhagia, Abnormal uterine bleeding, Hering's law of cure, MONARCH, Homoeopathy.

INTRODUCTION

ETYMOLOGY: The term 'menorrhagia' is from the Greek word, men meaning 'menses' and rrhagia meaning 'burst forth.'^[1]

DEFINITION: Menorrhagia refers to cyclic menstrual bleeding occurring at normal intervals, but with an excessive volume (more than 80 mL), an extended duration (longer than 7 days), or both. The term *menotaxis* is commonly used to describe prolonged bleeding.^[2]

INCIDENCE/PREVALENCE

- In the UK, 5% of women aged 30-49 years consult their general practitioners each year with menorrhagia. In New Zealand, 2-4% of primary-care consultations by premenopausal women are for menstrual problems.^[3]
- The World Health Organization estimates that 18 million women aged 30-55 perceive their menstrual bleeding as excessively heavy. However, reports indicate that only about 10% of these women have blood loss severe enough to cause anemia or meet the clinical definition of menorrhagia.^[4]

ETIOLOGY^[1]

Pelvic Causes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) and pelvic adhesions • Uterine fibroids and endometrial hyperplasia • Adenomyosis • Feminizing ovarian tumours • Endometriosis • Pelvic congestion and pelvic varicosities
Contraceptive-Related Causes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD) use • Post-tubal sterilization • Progestogen-only pills

Hormonal / Abnormal Uterine Bleeding (AUB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ovulatory causes: irregular ripening or shedding • Anovulatory causes: resting endometrium (accounts for ~80%) • Metropathia haemorrhagica • Stress- induced, emotional imbalance.
General Causes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blood dyscrasias • Coagulopathies • Thyroid dysfunction - Hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in initial stages. • Genital tuberculosis

INDICATORS FOR DIAGNOSING AND ASSESSING THE SEVERITY OF MENORRHAGIA^[2]

- Prolonged menstrual flow
- Passage of large blood clots
- Increased use of thick sanitary pads
- Presence of pallor
- Low haemoglobin levels

INVESTIGATIONS^[1]

Patients with menorrhagia require thorough evaluation. In addition to a physical examination, the following investigations are recommended.

- Complete hemogram.
- Bleeding time and clotting time.
- Thyroid profile, when indicated.
- Pelvic sonography / sonosalpingography; diagnostic laparoscopy.
- Endometrial assessment using ultrasound and curettage.
- Sonosalpingography, which can clearly identify submucous fibroids.
- Pelvic angiography when other tests fail to determine the cause—useful for detecting varicosities and arteriovenous fistula.
- Diagnostic hysteroscopy.

CASE REPORT

A 21-year-old female student presents with a sudden onset of painless menorrhagia persisting for 15–20 days. She attained menarche at 13 years, with consistently regular cycles every 40–45 days and a bright red menstrual flow lasting 3–5 days since menarche. Her family history is significant for diabetes mellitus and thyroid disorders on the maternal side, and hypertension on the paternal side. Constitutionally, she is fair, fatty, and flabby, with cold,

clammy, soft palms, a sanguine temperament, and a chilly, warm-seeking disposition. She has good thirst and marked constipation, particularly 1–2 days before menses, although she usually adapts to and tolerates her constipation without much distress. She has strong cravings for salty and oily foods.

Mentally and emotionally, she is quiet, timid, sensitive, reserved, and generally uncommunicative. She experiences intense anger and sadness but habitually suppresses these emotions. Her anger is rarely verbalized and instead presents as a pinkish-red facial flush. She is easily hurt, highly sensitive to trifles and criticism, and tends to withdraw during emotional stress. She prefers to weep alone, often feeling burdensome and expressing a desire to escape from her environment.

Importantly, 10–15 days before the onset of her current menstrual episode, her mother scolded her severely, questioning her future stability and earning capacity. This reprimand had a profound emotional impact, making her feel worthless and unvalued, triggering anguish and a desire to run away from home. This suppressed emotional hurt appears temporally related to the onset of her acute, prolonged uterine bleeding. Previously, she remained unconcerned even if her menses were delayed for up to 40 days, but on this occasion, when they did not appear even after 15 days, she became anxious and began taking various over-the-counter medicines suggested by different people. This anxiety, combined with the emotional insult, have contributed to the current menstrual disturbance.

The reportorial analysis^[5] upon selecting the rubrics shows.

Symptoms: 8 Remedies: 130 Applied Filter						
Remedy Name	Calc	Plat	Nux-v	Staph	Bell	Ign
Totality / Symptom Covered	13 / 8	10 / 4	7 / 3	7 / 3	6 / 4	6 / 3
[Kent] [Mind]Cheerful,gay,happy (see mirth):Constipated,when: (2)	2					
[Kent] [Mind]Company:Aversion to:Avoids the sight of people:Country away from people,...	1					
[Kent] [Mind]Anger,irascibility (see irritability,quarrelsome):Ailments after anger:V...	1	3	3	3	2	3
[Kent] [Mind]Rudeness (compare insolent):Ailments,from: (7)	2		1	3		
[Kent] [Genitalia female]Menses:Protracted: (91)	3	3	3		1	2
[Kent] [Mind]Anguish:Menses:During: (10)	1	2			2	1
[Kent] [Mind]Aversion:Persons,to certain: (7)	2					
[Kent] [Mind]Delusions,imagination,hallucinations,illusion:Strange:Familiar things :Seem: (...)	1	2		1	1	

Along with the repertorial analysis patient still has deciduous teeth [TEETH- DENTITION- difficult- milk tooth persists]; soft, cold, clammy perspiring palms confirming calcarea group. Thus, *Calcarea carbonicum* 30C single dose was prescribed in water dose on 1/8/25

MANAGEMENT

- Take absolute rest; avoid physical exertion, long standing, lifting weights.
- Maintain good hydration—at least 2–2.5 L/day.
- Use warm compress to lower abdominal discomfort if present.
- Maintain menstrual hygiene; change pads every 4–6 hours.
- Ensure 7-8hours of sleep.
- Avoid stress, late nights, and excessive screen time. Avoid travelling and strenuous exercise until bleeding reduces.
- Monitor bleeding pattern daily (colour, quantity, presence of clots).
- Foods to Include- Iron-rich foods like Spinach, beetroot, dates, figs, jaggery, ragi etc; Vitamin C sources-Lemon water, amla etc; Protein sources like Eggs, dal, paneer etc; Hydrating fluids like ORS, coconut water etc.
- Foods to Avoid: Caffeine: tea, coffee; Very spicy, oily food; Junk foods / packaged snacks.

FOLLOW UP

Date	Symptomatology	Treatment
16/8/25	Bleeding stopped after taking medicine within 1 day. Suffering from cold, runny nose & cough from 11/8/25 Improvement in general well-being.	<i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> 200C - 1 dose. Placebo x BD x 6pills x 15 days
3/9/25	Attained menses on time on 1/9/25. Flow is better, bright red in colour. No evident complaints	Placebo x BD x 6pills x 30 days
5/10/25	Good response, attained menses on time. No adverse complaints	Placebo x BD x 6pills x 30 days
4/11/25	Noticeably better in both mental & emotional sphere. No new menstrual complaints	Placebo x BD x 6pills x 30 days

According to Hering's law of cure^[6]- Cure takes place with symptoms disappearing from above - downwards, inside- outsides, centre to periphery, from more important to less important organ, in the reverse order of their appearance.

In this case, the presenting complaint of protracted menses corresponds to the AUPD layer, which represents the 5th level of suppression chart by Dr. Prafull Vijayakar. After administering the acute remedy which was also genetic constitutional similimum, the patient exhibited a shift in symptom expression: the menstrual pathology resolved, and upper respiratory tract symptoms emerged. This transition indicates a movement from a deeper pathological layer (AUPD) toward a more superficial layer, involving the endoderm-derived respiratory system, which corresponds to the 2nd layer.

Following the resolution of the transient respiratory symptoms, the patient experienced no further complaints, suggesting a favourable direction of cure, consistent with Hering's law - moving from deeper to more superficial, and from more vital to less vital organs.

Understanding by Psychoneuroendocrinoimmunological axis (PNEI): A thick endometrial lining or prolonged menstrual bleeding (menorrhagia/protracted menses) can occur for several well-studied reasons, such as: Hormonal imbalance (estrogen excess, low progesterone), Anovulatory cycles, Perimenopause, Fibroids or polyps, Thyroid dysfunction, Stress affecting hormonal regulation, Rarely, endometrial hyperplasia or other pathology.

According to physiology: Estrogen builds the endometrium, Progesterone stabilizes it, falling hormones cause shedding (menses). When these signals become irregular, the lining may become too thick and shed slowly or unevenly, causing prolonged bleeding.

In protracted menses, fluctuating or falling estrogen levels can cause emotional disturbances such as irritability, tearfulness, fatigue, and reduced stress tolerance. Since estrogen normally supports mood and energy, its imbalance during prolonged bleeding often contributes to heightened emotional sensitivity alongside the physical symptoms.

Whereas diminished or unstable progesterone levels often lead to emotional unease, as this hormone is central to maintaining calmness and psychological balance. When progesterone drops, women may experience anxiety, irritability, restlessness, and disturbed sleep, reflecting its usual role as a natural calming modulator. This emotional sensitivity can further intensify the distress associated with prolonged bleeding.

According to German New Medicine (GNM)^[7]: The endometrium is linked to themes of: Nest security, Protection, Nourishment, Fear related to family, home, or children, wanting to care for or protect for/by a child. (real or symbolic)

Conflict Theme- Thickening of the endometrial lining is interpreted as a response to a “nest insecurity conflict”. Examples like Feeling your home or family is unsafe, feeling unprotected, wanting to protect or nourish a child, Feeling emotionally abandoned, insecure, or threatened, wanting to hold the family together.

Biological Theme- GNM claims the endometrium thickens to create a “better nest”- More cushioning, more nourishment, more protection, A symbolic attempt to “give more love, warmth, and security”. This reflects GNM’s belief that the body adapts to emotional shocks with physical tissue changes.

Differential Remedies^[8,9]

Kali Carbonicum: Kali carbonicum differs from *Calcarea carbonica* by its rigid conventionality, strict rule-following, and fear of breaking norms duty-bound, serious, responsible nature rather than *Calcarea*’s homely simplicity material insecurity with marked anxiety, restlessness, irritability, and hypersensitivity strong fear of change, but arising from rigidity and rules, not from *Calcarea*’s need for comfort poor social ease and self-consciousness, especially in relationships. In short: Kali carb is rigid, rule-bound, anxious,

and conventional, whereas *Calcarea carb* is soft, homely, comfort-seeking, and security-oriented.

Natrum Carbonicum: More anxious, nervous, and timid than *Calcarea*; anxiety especially about socialising, meeting people, thunderstorms. Emotional pattern is Natrum-like but milder, less suppressed than *Natrum mur*; more anxiety, less depression. Physically thin, bony, delicate, freckled, with characteristic burning of soles/joints, unlike fleshy *Calcarea*. Seeks security like *Calcarea*, but from emotional sensitivity, not from love of routine or comfort. *Calcarea* is solid, homely, comfort-loving and stable; *Natrum carb* is fragile, nervous, socially anxious and easily overstimulated.

Essence of *Calcarea carbonica*:^[8,9] The patient's totality corresponds profoundly to the constitutional essence of *Calcarea carbonica*. The most characteristic features of the case highlight a personality that is slow, steady, security-oriented, deeply attached to the familiar, emotionally soft, and resistant to change - all of which represent the *Calcarea* archetype.

1. FUNDAMENTAL NEED FOR SECURITY & STABILITY- The central theme of the patient is a deep need for physical, emotional, and material security. Change produces anxiety, and the patient prefers stable routines and familiar environments. This keynote matches *Calcarea*'s core psychology, where security = familiarity. *Calcarea* avoids challenges not due to incapacity, but due to fear of stepping beyond her comfort zone.

2. SLOWNESS, GROUNDEDNESS & PRUDENT TEMPERAMENT - The patient reflects a slow, cautious, deliberate temperament, grounded in practicality rather than ambition or excitement. This "solid and plodding" nature is a classical trait of *Calcarea*, distinguishing her from fiery, outward, competitive remedies like *Lachesis* or *Sulphur*.

3. WORRY ABOUT THE FUTURE BUT COPING BY AVOIDANCE - The case reveals anticipatory worries especially about the future or possible misfortunes - yet without *Arsenicum*'s restlessness or fastidiousness. Instead, the patient copes through avoidance of change and by remaining within familiar surroundings. This pattern is distinctly *Calcarea*.

4. SIMPLICITY, HOMELINESS & PREFERENCE FOR COMFORT - The patient displays an unpretentious, simple nature with great love for homely comforts, routine domestic life, food, rest, and emotional warmth. *Calcarea*'s pleasures are modest yet deeply

rooted in physical and familial security. This pragmatic simplicity is a keynote distinguishing Calcarea from more intellectual or introspective remedies.

5. STRONG FAMILY ATTACHMENT & NURTURING DISPOSITION - A striking feature of the patient is intense bonding with the family, preference for being at home, emotional dependence on familiar people, and sentimentality. Calcarea individuals are the backbone of the family, offering stability, warmth, and dependability. The patient's tendency to feel homesick, avoid separation, and find safety within family supports strongly point to Calcarea.

6. MILDNESS, SENTIMENTALITY & SOFT EMOTIONAL EXPRESSION - The patient expresses emotions gently, tending toward quiet tears, self-pity, and mild melancholy rather than dramatic or explosive reactions. This emotional softness is quintessential Calcarea- sentimental, nurturing, and stable, unlike the fluctuating emotionality of Pulsatilla or the deep grief of Natrum.

7. TIMIDITY, UNDERACHIEVEMENT & FEAR OF RESPONSIBILITY- The patient's history of avoiding challenges, withdrawing from opportunities, or giving up when success demands greater responsibility is a classical Calcarea mental characteristic. Kent's observation - "right in the midst of success he quits his business" - perfectly captures this theme.

8. STUBBORNNESS & RESISTANCE TO IMPOSED CHANGE - Calcarea clings to the familiar and becomes obstinate when pressured or rushed. The patient's resistance to new situations and slow adaptability confirm this rubric.

9. PHYSICAL CONSTITUTION - Calcarea individuals typically show: soft, fleshy build; tendency to weight gain; pale, milky, chalk-like complexion.

10. REMEDY RELATIONSHIP^[10]

- HOT – Cham, Con, Puls, Sulph, Bism, Lyc, Plat, Sars.
- CHILLY – Agar, Rhus, China, Cup, Ipec, Nit-Ac, Nux- V, Graph, Nat-C, Phos, Sep, Sil, Bell, Ther.

MONARCH (Improved Version of Modified Naranjo Criteria for Homoeopathy)^[11]

S.no.	Domain	Current Observation in the Case	Points
1.	Was there an improvement in the main symptom or condition for which the Homeopathic medicine was prescribed?	Sudden painless menorrhagia of 15–20 days stopped completely within 24 hours after administration of <i>Calcarea carbonica</i> 200C	+2
2.	Did the clinical improvement occur within a plausible time frame relative to the drug intake?	Clinical improvement occurred within a plausible time frame following drug intake	+2
3.	Was there an initial aggravation of symptoms?	No aggravation observed	0
4.	Did the effect encompass more than the main symptom or condition (i.e., were other symptoms ultimately improved or changed)?	Improvement in general well-being, respiratory symptoms, and mental–emotional state	+1
5.	Did overall well-being improve? (Suggest using validated scale)	Patient reported subjective improvement in well-being and emotional stability (clinically observed)	+1
6.	A Direction of cure: did some symptoms improve in the opposite order of the development of symptoms of the disease?	Resolution of the acute pathological condition (menorrhagia) preceded improvement in general and emotional symptoms, suggesting reverse order of symptom development.	+1
7.	Direction of cure: did at least two of the following aspects apply to the order of improvement of symptoms: –from organs of more importance to those of less importance? –from deeper to more superficial aspects of the individual? –from the top downwards?	Improvement observed from deeper (mental/emotional) to more superficial levels and from more vital organs to general health.	+1
8.	Are there alternate causes (other than the medicine) that—with a high probability— could have caused the improvement? (Consider known course of disease, other forms of treatment, and other clinically relevant interventions)	No conventional medication, hormonal therapy, or other intervention was used; spontaneous resolution after prolonged bleeding was unlikely.	+2
9.	Was the Health improvement confirmed by any objective evidence? (e.g., laboratory test, clinical observation, etc.)	Cessation of bleeding and subsequent regularization of menstrual cycles confirmed through repeated clinical follow-up.	+1
10.	Did repeat dosing, if conducted, create similar clinical improvement?	Repeat dosing was not required; sustained improvement was maintained with placebo alone.	0
	Total		11

INTERPRETATION - A MONARCH score ≥ 9 indicates a definite causal relationship between the homeopathic intervention and the observed clinical outcome. The score of 11 in this case supports a strong causal attribution of the patient's improvement to *Calcarea carbonica*.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates that individualized homeopathic prescribing may be effective in managing acute functional presentations such as protracted menorrhagia, particularly when precipitated by emotional stress. The rapid cessation of uterine bleeding within 24 hours following administration of the indicated remedy, *Calcarea carbonica*, suggests a prompt therapeutic response in this acute setting. In addition to immediate control of bleeding, the patient exhibited sustained improvement in emotional stability and normalization of menstrual cycles during subsequent follow-up. The clinical outcome was further evaluated using the MONARCH (Improved Modified Naranjo) criteria, which yielded a score consistent with a definite causal relationship between the homeopathic intervention and the observed improvement. Application of this standardized outcome-assessment tool strengthens the methodological rigor of the case and supports attribution of the clinical response to the prescribed remedy rather than to spontaneous resolution or confounding factors. Overall, this case underscores the potential value of constitutional homeopathic treatment as a safe and holistic approach in selected acute gynecological conditions, while also highlighting the importance of structured assessment tools such as MONARCH to enhance transparency and reproducibility in homeopathic case reporting.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Acute menorrhagia following emotional stress treated successfully with homeopathy.
- Individualized prescription of *Calcarea carbonica* based on totality.
- Bleeding ceased within 24 hours without hormonal therapy.
- Sustained improvement confirmed on follow-up.
- Causal attribution supported by MONARCH score.

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